

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360515588>

BIXO, a student-led CubeSat mission for education and astrobiology research

Conference Paper · February 2022

CITATIONS

0

READS

161

11 authors, including:

Alejandro Camanzo Mariño
University of Vigo

5 PUBLICATIONS 3 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Manuel Diz-Folgar
University of Vigo

2 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Pablo Chedas
University of Vigo

2 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Fernando Aguado Agelet
University of Vigo

23 PUBLICATIONS 114 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

ChemiFish [View project](#)

Surface-enhanced Raman scattering sensors [View project](#)

BIXO, a student-led CubeSat mission for education and astrobiology research

Alejandro Camanzo¹, Manuel Diz-Folgar¹, Manuel Vale-Xoubanova¹, Pablo Chedas Castro¹, Pedro M. Carro Parafita¹, Lucía Amaro-Losada², Fernando Aguado-Agelet², Gustavo Bodelón-González², Carmen Sieiro², Isabel Pastoriza-Santos², and Jorge Pérez-Juste²

¹UVigo SpaceLab, Spain

²University of Vigo, Spain

25th of February 2022

Abstract

BIXO, Bacteriological Intercommunication eXperiment in Orbit is a CubeSat mission being developed by a team of university students of various engineering disciplines, with the consultancy of several professors. The objective of this mission is twofold: first, to provide an active environment for students to acquire first-hand experience in the development and management of a challenging engineering project, and secondly, to study how microorganisms behave in the space environment, by means of an astrobiology experiment flying aboard the CubeSat (1). This poster focuses on the status of the project, concerning the CONOPS, mission and system requirements, as well as the biological payload design.

The goal of the CubeSat payload is to conduct astrobiology scientific experiments with the objective to monitor bacterial communication under spaceflight conditions. Quorum Sensing (QS) is a fundamental cell-to-cell communication process that allows bacteria to sense their population density and control gene expression accordingly (2). QS is involved in bacterial physiology and virulence. In

particular, pathogenic traits such as biofilm formation, the biosynthesis of antimicrobials, horizontal gene transfer, and adaptive immunity heavily rely on this form of bacterial communication (3)(4). Remarkably, it is still unknown whether bacteria can engage in active QS under spaceflight conditions.

The expected outcome of this project is to obtain a better understanding of the Quorum Sensing process in the space environment. Additionally, the infrastructure and organization of the student lab will be demonstrated, allowing future student-led space missions to be developed, and establishing a sustainable learning environment for students and young engineers.

1 Introduction

Solar and cosmic radiation and microgravity have been shown to affect the virulence, growth kinetics and biofilm formation of microorganisms, thereby affecting the health, safety, or performance of the crew in spaceflight missions. Remarkably, bacterial pathogens rely heavily on Quorum Sensing systems to control the expression of genes required for pathogenesis.

It is still unknown whether bacteria can engage in active Quorum Sensing under spaceflight conditions, and due to the above-mentioned implications in bacterial physiology and virulence, its effects need to be understood and addressed for future space missions.

Since Quorum Sensing has profound effects both on bacterial physiology and behaviour, an understanding of their impacts throughout space flights is of paramount importance. The BIXO Mission will try and uncover the effects of the space environment on Quorum Sensing processes.

2 State of the Art

The first microorganism which travelled aboard a CubeSat was the *Escherichia Coli* in 2006. It is a bacterium that is commonly found in the large intestine of humans and other warm-blooded animals. The mission was the GeneSat-1, and it was the first biological CubeSat launched by NASA and the chosen orbit was LEO (450 km). The research study had two main goals: the study of the effects of microgravity and the detection of the levels of GFP expressed in living cultures. It was a 3U CubeSat where the biological payload occupied 2 CubeSat volumes (2U). Microfluidic technology was used with bacterial cultures in 12-well microfluidic cards with 110- μ L culture wells. The measurements were made with one blue-LED-excited fluorescent detection system per well that quantified the levels of light emitted by a fluorescent protein. The duration of the main experiment was around 6 days, and they found that the growth rates of the flight samples decreased. It was a success because the experiment demonstrated that it is possible to conduct significant science in space with the use of small spacecraft.

In 2009, PharmaSat was launched. It contained *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* which is budding yeast with a lot of interesting properties:

1. It shares with humans hundreds of homologous genes that govern essential cellular processes,

2. It's relatively easy genetic manipulation,
3. It can be desiccated yet remain viable for long periods and
4. Yeast can survive the constraints of long-duration space flight as well as extensive prelaunch periods without substantial life support.

The PharmaSat is a 3U CubeSat with 2 biological payload CubeSat volumes. 3-LED optical emission/detection system. The main goal of the mission was the study of the effects of microgravity on yeast susceptibility to antifungal drugs.

In 2014, the SporeSat mission carried a fern, the *Ceratopteris richardii* (Pteridaceae) which is a fast-growing tropical fern, used globally in research laboratories. The SporeSat CubeSat is a 3U CubeSat with 2 biological payload CubeSat volumes (2U). Instead of using microfluidic technology, it was the first CubeSat with an electrochemical sensor system in a LOC format. It had 3 BioCD lab-on-a-chip devices for real-time measurements of calcium signalling. Two of these chips were centrifuged, and the third one remained in microgravity. The main mission objective was to study the effects of microgravity on the calcium ion channel activity of germinating fern spores. The orbit was also LEO (325 km). The mission was not successful due to the LED failure on the ground and in space, only the demo of minicentrifuges was a success.

Other missions that have previously flown are O/OREOS and EcAMSat. O/OREOS was the first nanosatellite to incorporate two completely independent and interchangeable payloads, it was a 3U CubeSat with two 1U independent biological modules: SESLO and SEVO. Each payload conducted a distinct demonstration experiment. They selected two microorganisms: the *Bacillus subtilis* and the *Halorubrum chaoviatoris*. EcAMSat was a 6U CubeSat with 3 CubeSat volumes for the bio payload launched in 2017, the goal of the mission was to investigate the effects of microgravity on the antibiotic

Figure 1: Concept of Operations

resistance of the bacteria *Escherichiacoli*. The orbit was also LEO(400 km).

3 Concept of operations

To accomplish the scientific objectives of the Mission, we will implement bacterial cultures of *C. violaceum* wild strain that produces violacein in response to QS and an isogenic QS mutant strain that does not produce violacein. Violacein production will be monitored at OD590 nm in the wild strain, and bacterial growth at OD600 nm in the mutant strain. Concurrently, a set of similar samples will be monitored by the User Segment as a control group and to monitor the differences, if any, between the on-orbit and on-ground samples.

4 Challenges

The integration of a biological payload in a 2U CubeSat creates several technical challenges, arising from both technical limitations and inherent characteristics of the CubeSat form factor. The main challenges addressed on this mission are the following:

4.1 Pressure Vessel

The addition of a pressurized environment for the biological samples increases the time and effort required in verification processes necessary to validate the biological payload of the mission, especially since CubeSats do not often carry pressurized equipment.

However, the *ECSS-E-ST-32-02C*, combined with ESA's *Tailored ECSS Engineering Standards for In orbit Demonstration CubeSat Projects* (document reference: *TEC-SY/182/2013/SPD/RW*) provides a clear path forward for the verification of the design.

4.2 Miniaturization

Miniaturization of devices commonly used in biological laboratories, where they are not subject to the stringent requirements on size, weight, and power (SWaP) present on CubeSat systems.

Microfluidic Lab-on-a-chip devices provide a good platform for miniaturization of the fluidic devices required for the experiment, allowing several different devices (mixing, homogenization, sample distribution, etc) in a very small footprint.

4.3 Sample preservation

Long term sample preservation through AIV processes, launcher integration and LEOP phases requires the use of lyophilization and on-orbit microfluidic systems, increasing complexity.

4.4 Thermal control

Thermal control is a leading requirement, as temperature is a key factor on the bacterial culture's growth and survivability. This necessitates the integration of a heater system and thermal insulation on the instrument to maintain adequate conditions. The samples, once rehydrated, need to maintain a temperature between 5-30 degrees at all times.

References

- [1] S. Tieze, L. Liddell, S. S. Maria, and S. Bhattacharya, "Biosentinel: A biological cubesat for deep space exploration," *Astrobiology*, vol. 20, no. 8, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1089/ast.2019.2068>
- [2] M. Whiteley, S. P. Diggle, and E. P. Greenberg, "Progress in and promise of bacterial quorum sensing research," *Nature*, vol. 551, no. 7680, pp. 313-320, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature24624>
- [3] S. T. Rutherford and B. L. Bassler, "Bacterial quorum sensing: its role in virulence and possibilities for its control. cold spring harbor perspectives in medicine," *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Med*, vol. 2, no. 11, 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.A012427>
- [4] L. Cui, X. Wang, D. Huang, Y. Zhao, J. Feng, Q. Lu, Q. Pu, and et al., "Crispr-cas3 of salmonella upregulates bacterial biofilm formation and virulence to host cells by targeting quorum-sensing systems," *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Med*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 53, 2020. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9010053>